

and tillering indicate that silvershoots stimulate tillering. However, it can also be argued that hills containing more tillers have greater probability of attack. An estimate of partial correlation coefficient between silvershoots and panicles was -0.32 , significant at $p = 0.05$.

Partial regression analysis using co-

variance model $y = f(\text{Tr.}; X_1 X_2 X_3)$ was done to estimate losses caused by silvershoots. The resulting partial regression equation was $y = 1.84 - 0.40 X_1 + 0.46 X_2$, where y stands for panicle, X_1 for silvershoot, and X_2 for tiller. The estimate of R , the multiple correlation coefficient, was 0.78 and significant at

$P = 0.01$.

Both the partial regression coefficients were also significant at $P \leq 0.01$. The partial regression equation suggests that the expected net effect of a unit increase in the number of silvershoots is a 0.40 reduction panicle number. \curvearrowright

Leaffolder population monitoring using a sex pheromone

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Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée is an important rice

pest in Sri Lanka. Insecticides are the only practical control and proper timing of application is essential to obtain maximum control benefits.

In a preliminary study, the synthetic female sex pheromone of *C. medinalis* was tested for usefulness as a monitoring device to determine the correct time of insecticide treatment.

Traps consisted of rubber septum dispensers containing the pheromone placed about 5 cm above a circular tray containing water with a small amount of detergent. They were placed about 25 m

apart in a 1-ha field planted to Bg 380-2. Trapped moths were counted daily. Crop damage was estimated at 10-day intervals until harvest.

Peak crop damage was observed 10-20 days after the peak moth count (see figure). Peak moth count may represent the period of mating and oviposition followed by hatching and early larval feeding, which would be the most suitable time for insecticide treatment. Pheromone traps can be used to determine the correct time of insecticide application for leaffolder control. \curvearrowright

Insect damage on azolla in Thailand

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Caseworm *Nymphula enixalis* (Swinhoe) and chironomids *Chironomus glauciventris* Kieffer and *C. (Polypedium) anticus* Johannsen are the most important insects attacking azolla in Thailand. During 1979-80 yield loss assessments to determine the significance of insect damage on azolla were conducted at Sakolnakorn, Ubolratchatani, and Sanpahtawng (Cheingmai) rice

experiment stations, Azolla was grown in two $10 \times 20\text{-m}^2$ field plots. One plot was sprayed with $0.3 \text{ kg ai mono-crotophos/ha}$ at 7 and 14 days after inoculation; the other was not treated.

Insects caused significant yield losses. Thirteen of 34 crops were destroyed or produced no yield (see table). Yield from treated plots averaged 10.5 t/ha ; that from untreated plots had an average 51% yield loss.

Azolla yields differed significantly between sites. Yields were greater at Ubolratchatani, where insect damage was less severe. Damage was most severe at Sanpahtawng where 50% of cultivated azolla produced no yield and average yield loss was 80%. More insect damage occurred during the summer

Yields and yield losses of azolla cultivated at 3 rice experiment stations in Thailand, 1979-80.

Site	Total crops	Crop failure ^a	Azolla fresh weight (t/ha)		Yield loss (%)
			Treated ^b plot	Untreated plot	
Ubolratchatani	12	4	13	8.2	37
Sakolnakorn	10	3	9.8	5.6	43
Sanpahtawng	12	6	8.5	1.7	80
Total or average	34	13	10.5	5.1	51

^aNo. of crops from untreated plots that produced no yield. ^b $0.3 \text{ kg ai monocrotophos/ha}$ was applied 7 and 14 days after planting.

Male moths trapped (no./10 trap nights)

Damaged leaves (%)

Comparison of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* damage to transplanted rice and moth catches in a sex pheromone trap.